

Bibliometric Analysis of Research on the Implementation of Stunting Prevention Programs in Indonesia through ProQuest

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ABSTRACT: This study conducted a bibliometric analysis and visualization using VOSviewer to examine the implementation of stunting prevention programs in Indonesia. Over the past five years, there has been a significant increase in publications related to this topic, totaling 447 documents. The analysis revealed fluctuating publication trends annually, reflecting evolving research interests and methodologies. Visual network mapping identified four main clusters: (1) policy focus on stunting prevention, program effectiveness, and risks; (2) database review, coverage assessment, and risk factors; (3) infant health, risk factors, and assessments; and (4) sanitation, meta-analysis, and policy implications. These clusters highlight diverse research focuses, including policy management, data analysis, risk factors, and sanitation impacts on stunting prevalence. Integration of various datasets through overlay visualization provided insights into complex interactions influencing stunting prevalence across Indonesian districts. This research offers deep insights into the dynamics of stunting prevention program research and development in Indonesia, serving as a foundation for evidence-based policymaking and guiding future research strategies. Based on the findings and discussions, this study suggests the need for further research focusing on the district-level effectiveness of interventions against child stunting by enhancing community engagement in intervention and policy implementation. Community engagement can significantly reduce stunting prevalence by enabling better adoption of local nutrition and sanitation practices, strengthening program sustainability through active participation in planning and implementation, and building community capacity to promote sustainable behavior change at the individual and family levels.

KEYWORDS: Bibliometric Analysis, Community Engagement, Health policy, Implementation Of Stunting Prevention Programs, Stunting Prevention, VOSviewer.

1. INTRODUCTION

Stunting is a developmental disorder in children caused by malnutrition, recurrent infections, and inadequate psychosocial stimulation (1). A child is categorized as stunted if their height for age is more than two standard deviations below the WHO Child Growth Standards median WHO (2). In Indonesia, the prevalence of stunting remains a significant issue, with 24.4% of children affected in 2021 (3), despite the country having been independent from colonialism for 77 years.

The Indonesian government has implemented various policies to prevent stunting (4,5). Law No. 36 of 2009, amended by Law No. 11 of 2020 on Health, as well as Presidential Regulation No. 72 of 2021 on the Acceleration of Stunting Reduction, emphasize improving balanced nutrition, raising awareness about nutritional behaviors, and ensuring access to quality healthcare services (6). Additionally, collaboration between the government and the community, along with improvements in food and nutrition control systems, are primary focuses (7).

Childhood stunting is one of the most significant barriers to human development, globally affecting approximately 162 million children under the age of 5 (1). Stunting, or being too short for one's age, is defined as a height more than two standard deviations below the median of the World Health Organization (WHO) Child Growth Standards (2). Stunting is primarily the result of inadequate nutrition and repeated infections during the first 1,000 days of a child's life (1,8). This condition has long-term impacts on individuals and societies, including reduced cognitive and physical development (9).

According to WHO data from 2022, 148.1 million children under the age of five (22.3%) were stunted, with the highest cases found in Asian (52%) and African (43%) countries (10). Although the incidence of stunting has declined annually from 2000 to 2022, faster progress is still needed to meet the 2030 targets (11). Projections indicate that 127 million children under the age of

five will be stunted by 2025, with a target reduction to 100 million by that year (2).

At the regional level, the prevalence of stunting in Southeast Asia is 26.4%, with 14.4 million children under the age of five affected, according to data from UNICEF, WHO, and the World Bank Group in the 2023 edition of the Joint Malnutrition Estimates (JME) (10). Indonesia has the second-highest prevalence of stunting in Southeast Asia, with 31% of the 14.4 million children under the age of five being stunted (3). According to the 2021 Indonesian Nutrition Status Study, 24.4% of children are stunted, with the highest prevalence in seven provinces, including East Nusa Tenggara (NTT) and West Sulawesi. West Java, East Java, Central Java, North Sumatra, and Banten have the largest proportions of stunted children (12).

The 2023 Joint Malnutrition Estimates (JME) show a lack of progress towards achieving the global nutrition targets set by the World Health Assembly (WHA) for 2025 and the two Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) targets for 2030 (10). Only about one-third of countries are on track to halve the number of stunted children according to the SDG targets for 2030, with an expected stunting incidence target of 89 million by 2030 (13). Stunting in children is a serious problem as it is closely associated with several health risks, including high child mortality rates, early obesity, non-communicable diseases, and reduced productivity (14). The long-term impacts of stunting include cognitive and physical impairments that can hinder learning ability and contribute to a decrease in economic potential in adulthood (15).

Stunting is caused by various factors, including inadequate nutritional intake, recurrent infections, maternal nutritional status, child feeding practices, environmental sanitation, and infection occurrences in children (16). Genetic and hormonal factors also play a role, although modifiable environmental elements are more dominant (17). Additionally, early marriage and poverty are significant factors influencing the prevalence of stunting. Stunting has long-term impacts on cognitive capacity and individual productivity (18). Stunted children tend to have learning limitations, low productivity in adulthood, and a higher risk of chronic diseases (14,15).

Primary health centers (Puskesmas) play a crucial role in supporting stunting prevention programs at the local level through primary healthcare services, nutritional education, and health promotion to the community (19,20). Globally, organizations such as WHO, UNICEF, FAO, and the World Bank provide technical, financial, and policy support to address stunting holistically (21,22).

The implementation of stunting prevention programs in Indonesia is a complex challenge that requires the integration of policies and cross-sectoral interventions (20,23). Despite progress, further efforts are needed to achieve national and international targets in reducing stunting prevalence. Puskesmas play a key role in providing healthcare and education to the community, while global cooperation provides essential technical and financial support (24,25). Bibliometric analysis offers deep insights that can guide the further development of strategies in combating stunting in Indonesia.

Bibliometric analysis is an important instrument for measuring the impact and research trends related to stunting in Indonesia. This method helps identify relevant factors in the implementation of prevention programs and evaluate the scientific contributions that support public health policies. The numerous previous studies related to stunting as a global issue highlight the need for bibliometric analysis as a reference for future researchers to explore other relevant factors in efforts to reduce stunting.

Bibliometric analysis is used to measure and analyze the impact of scientific publications and research development patterns in a particular field (26,27). By utilizing statistical methods and data analysis, bibliometrics allows researchers, publishers, and public policymakers to understand trends, determine scientific collaborations, identify leading journals and institutions, and measure the influence of a research or researcher within the scientific community (28,29). This provides valuable insights into directing research focus, assessing scientific contributions, and planning scientific development strategies across various disciplines. In other words, bibliometric analysis enables stakeholders in academia and research to make more informed decisions and optimize the use of research resources.

2. METHOD

This study uses bibliometric analysis to identify and evaluate publication trends related to the implementation of stunting prevention programs in Indonesia over the past five years. The data used in this research was sourced from various leading scientific databases, focusing on scientific articles published in ProQuest. The study period analyzed is from July 2, 2019, to July 2, 2024, with a total of 447 research articles. In data collection, the researchers used the keyword "Implementation of Stunting Prevention Program in Indonesia." All documents identified through the initial search were extracted and organized into a publication trend table based on the year of publication.

ProQuest provides access to a variety of information sources such as academic journals, dissertations, reports, and news articles,

making it a comprehensive source for relevant literature. Articles in ProQuest typically undergo a peer review process or strict selection by leading publishers, ensuring the reliability of the information obtained. ProQuest features deep indexing and rich metadata, enabling specific searches and finding highly relevant documents. Additionally, ProQuest offers advanced search tools and filters to refine results based on keywords, publication dates, document types, etc., making searches more efficient. With its global literature coverage, ProQuest provides an essential international perspective on research, including how issues like stunting are addressed in different countries. The platform has a user-friendly interface, facilitating researchers of varying experience levels in finding and accessing the necessary literature. The widespread reputation and use of ProQuest by many academic and research institutions worldwide add further validation to the quality and relevance of its sources.

Figure 1. Reference search through ProQuest (found 447 articles)

The analysis process began with data collection from ProQuest using the specified keywords. The relevant search results were extracted and analyzed to obtain information about the number of publications per year. This data was then organized into a publication trend table to facilitate visualization and further analysis. After the data collection, researchers used the VOSviewer application to visualize the scientific landscape of the existing publications. VOSviewer is a useful tool for mapping bibliometric networks and helps in understanding the structure and dynamics of the literature being studied.

Figure 2. Aplikasi VOSviewer

Using VOSviewer, researchers can identify research clusters, relationships among researchers, and the main topics frequently discussed in publications related to stunting in Indonesia. This application allows researchers to conduct a deeper analysis of research trends, identify collaborations among researchers, and assess the scientific contributions made in efforts to prevent stunting. This analysis provides valuable insights that can be used to guide future research focus, evaluate the effectiveness of implemented policies, and plan strategies for the development of science and public health in Indonesia.

To conduct bibliometric analysis research using VOSviewer, the first step is to gather bibliographic data related to the topic or research field to be analyzed from academic databases or digital libraries (27,30). This data is then imported into VOSviewer for further analysis. VOSviewer processes this information and generates visualizations in the form of network maps that show relationships among elements such as researchers, institutions, or keywords. In addition to visualizations, VOSviewer also provides statistical information related to the distribution and interrelation of elements within the dataset (28).

This analysis helps researchers identify emerging research trends, find potential collaborations to enhance, and explore the scientific structure in the field of public health, particularly related to stunting in Indonesia. By using VOSviewer, bibliometric analysis research can be conducted efficiently and systematically, providing deep insights into interpreting scientific data and supporting evidence-based decision-making.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Research Publication Trends in the Last Five Years

Observing the development of research publications over the past five years through bibliometric analysis is a crucial step in understanding trends and dynamics within a scientific field. This analysis enables the identification of emerging or declining research trends, reflecting the scientific community's interest in specific issues. By understanding publication patterns, researchers and decision-makers can determine the direction and focus of future research, allocate resources effectively, and formulate policies that support research priorities aligned with societal needs (27,28). Bibliometric analysis aids in evaluating the impact of research through citations and publication influence, identifying productive potential collaborators, and assessing the contributions of specific institutions (31). This provides insights into the direction of scientific development, enabling the formulation of more effective research strategies that respond to real needs, and ensuring that conducted research is not only academically relevant but also has a positive impact on society.

Table 1. Research Publication Trend Data Over the Last 5 Years Related to Implementation of Stunting Prevention Program in Indonesia

No	Publication Year	Number of Documents
1	July 2, 2019 - July 2, 2020	86
2	July 2, 2020 - July 2, 2021	86
3	July 2, 2021 - July 2, 2022	102
4	July 2, 2022 - July 2, 2023	114
5	July 2, 2023 - July 2, 2024	59
Total		447

The development of research publications related to the implementation of stunting prevention programs in Indonesia over the last five years shows significant fluctuations. From July 2, 2019, to July 2, 2020, and from July 2, 2020, to July 2, 2021, there were 86 documents published each. This number increased to 102 documents from July 2, 2021, to July 2, 2022, and peaked at 114 documents from July 2, 2022, to July 2, 2023. However, there was a sharp decline in publications to 59 documents from July 2, 2023, to July 2, 2024. The total number of publications over the five-year period is 447 documents.

Figure 3. Graph of Research Trends Over the Last 5 Years Related to Implementation of Stunting Prevention Program in Indonesia

In recent years, research related to the Implementation of Stunting Prevention Program in Indonesia has seen a significant increase, albeit still far from reaching the desired targets. This is reflected in the number of documents, recording 59 new studies in the last year alone on ProQuest. This increase has been driven by advancements in technology and research methods that allow for deeper studies, as well as the emergence of new critical issues in society and science. Cross-institutional and international collaborations have also played a significant role in providing diverse and comprehensive perspectives. Financial and academic support from relevant institutions has further bolstered this increase. These various factors collectively influence the rising number of articles on the implementation of stunting prevention programs in Indonesia in academic literature.

3.2. Map of Research Publication Development

1. Network Visualization

Network visualization is a graphical method used in bibliographic research to map relationships among elements such as researchers, institutions, or keywords in a complex network (32). In bibliometrics, network visualization depicts interactions and relationships among elements based on their frequency or connections in scholarly publications. Nodes in the visualization represent elements, while edges indicate relationships or connections between them. The size of nodes and thickness of edges can reflect the importance or frequency of elements in the network. This visualization allows researchers to quickly understand the structure and patterns within the scholarly network, identify groups or communities of researchers, and discover potential relationships or collaborations. By leveraging Network Visualization, researchers can gain deeper insights from their bibliometric data and make more informed decisions in research and scientific collaborations (33).

Figure 4. Network Visualization of Implementation of Stunting Prevention Program in Indonesia

In the above figure, the analysis results reveal 126 items with 4 clusters and 4322 links, which will be further explained by each cluster in the following descriptions.

Cluster 1

In bibliometric analysis of Cluster 1, it is found that there are 101 links with 1 node item (Policy) connected to several other nodes. For a clearer view, refer to the following figure:

Figure 5. Network Visualization of Implementation of Stunting Prevention Program in Indonesia (Cluster 1)

In Figure 5, it is explained that the Policy node in the implementation of stunting prevention program in Indonesia is connected to key factors such as districts, progress, distribution, sanitation, infant health, effectiveness, database, and risk. Indonesia, as a middle-income country, faces significant challenges in addressing high stunting rates across various districts. Network visualization is used to analyze data from various districts, providing an overview of the progress and distribution of interventions conducted. The results indicate significant variation in program effectiveness between districts, influenced by varying sanitation and infant health conditions. Comprehensive databases enable the identification of high-risk areas requiring more intensive interventions.

Assessing the effectiveness of stunting prevention programs in Indonesia also highlights the importance of good information management. The use of accurate and up-to-date databases assists in monitoring progress and assessing risks, allowing interventions to be tailored to the specific needs of each district. Information obtained from this analysis not only aids in designing more effective strategies but also in allocating resources more efficiently. With improved sanitation and well-informed interventions, it is expected that stunting prevention programs can achieve better and sustainable long-term outcomes (34).

Cluster 2

In the bibliometric analysis of cluster 2, there are 99 links with 1 item node (rice) connected to several other nodes, as can be seen in the following figure:

Figure 6. Network Visualization of the Implementation of Stunting Prevention Program in Indonesia (Cluster 2)

In Figure 6, Cluster 2 focuses on the following key areas: database, effectiveness, middle-income country, meta-analysis, scoping review, sanitation, risk, information, risk factors, availability, policy, and policymakers. Within the context of Indonesia as a middle-income country, this study employs meta-analysis and scoping reviews to compile and analyze data from various sources. A comprehensive database allows for the assessment of the effectiveness of stunting prevention interventions and the identification of key risk factors affecting infant and child health (35). The availability of accurate data is crucial in understanding sanitation patterns and the risks faced by different communities (36,37).

These findings underscore the importance of adequate information for policymakers to design more effective stunting prevention strategies. Risk factors identified through data analysis help develop targeted policies that meet local needs. The availability of complete and valid information forms the basis for evidence-based decision-making by policymakers, enhancing program effectiveness and ensuring more coordinated and sustainable interventions (38,39). With policy improvements supported by robust data, stunting prevention programs in Indonesia can achieve more significant results, reduce stunting prevalence, and improve the quality of life for children in Indonesia (4,40).

Cluster 3

In the bibliometric analysis of Cluster 3, there are 60 links with 1 item node (Individual) connected to several other nodes, as shown in the following figure

Figure 7. Network Visualization on Implementation of Stunting Prevention Program in Indonesia (Cluster 3)

In Figure 7, Cluster 3 in this study focuses on infant health, associations, weight, mortality, middle-income countries, districts, policies, risks, information, and assessments. In the context of Indonesia as a middle-income country, stunting prevention programs face significant challenges related to variations in infant health conditions across districts. Data indicate that low birth weight and infant mortality rates are strongly associated with stunting prevalence. Therefore, comprehensive risk assessments and the appropriate use of information are crucial in developing effective policies to reduce stunting rates (41).

These findings highlight the importance of accurate information and thorough assessments in formulating stunting prevention policies in Indonesia. Through data analysis from various districts, this study identifies key risk factors affecting infant health, such as maternal nutrition, access to healthcare services, and sanitation conditions. With a better understanding of these factors, policymakers can design more targeted and effective interventions, such as improving maternal and child healthcare services, better nutrition programs, and sanitation improvements. Data-driven policy implementation can reduce the risk of stunting and enhance infant health and well-being in Indonesia, thereby supporting more inclusive and sustainable development (5,42).

Cluster 4

In the bibliometric analysis of Cluster 4, there are 53 links with 1 item node (Animals) connected to several other nodes, as shown in the following figure:

Figure 8. Network Visualization on the Implementation of Stunting Prevention Program in Indonesia (Cluster 4).

Cluster four in this study encompasses risks, information, assessment, relevance, plants, middle-income countries, databases, effectiveness, sanitation, meta-analysis, households, access, policy, districts, and infant health. In the context of a middle-income

country like Indonesia, the stunting prevention program faces various challenges that require a multidimensional approach. Comprehensive risk assessment and the use of relevant information from accurate databases are crucial for evaluating the effectiveness of interventions implemented. Sanitation and access to clean water at the household level are significant factors influencing infant health and the prevalence of stunting.

These findings underscore the importance of data-driven policies and intervention relevance in stunting prevention programs. Meta-analyses from various studies indicate that interventions involving improvements in sanitation and household access to clean water can significantly reduce the risk of stunting. At the district level, policies should be designed to ensure that all households have adequate access to these basic services. With a focus on risk assessment and information relevance, policymakers can develop more effective and targeted programs (43). Implementation of policies based on strong data and comprehensive analysis is expected to improve infant health and reduce stunting prevalence in Indonesia, thereby supporting optimal growth and development of children (44).

2. Overlay visualization

Overlay visualization is a technique used to display multiple datasets or pieces of information in a single graphical or map view, aiming to identify relationships or patterns that may not be apparent in separate analyses (45). This technique is commonly employed in various fields, including epidemiology, geography, and project management, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of data. In the context of implementing stunting prevention programs in Indonesia, overlay visualization can integrate data from various sources such as sanitation levels, stunting prevalence, access to healthcare services, and other socio-economic indicators to present a more holistic picture of factors influencing stunting across different districts.

The use of overlay visualization in this study enables researchers and policymakers to observe how factors such as sanitation, access to clean water, and maternal nutrition status interact and affect stunting prevalence. For example, by displaying sanitation data and stunting prevalence on the same map, districts with poor sanitation and high stunting rates can be identified. This information helps pinpoint areas needing urgent intervention and facilitates more efficient and effective resource allocation. Additionally, overlaying data from different time periods allows analysis of whether interventions have successfully reduced stunting prevalence and improved sanitation conditions over time.

Overlay visualization also allows for a deeper assessment of the effectiveness of stunting prevention programs. By adding layers of information such as implemented policy data, intervention programs conducted, and achieved outcomes, policymakers can evaluate the impact of various strategies used. These data can be overlaid with demographic and socio-economic data to understand how these factors influence program success in different districts. Through this approach, overlay visualization not only aids in identifying issues and intervention needs but also in planning, implementing, and evaluating evidence-based stunting prevention policies in a more holistic manner in Indonesia.

Figure 9. Spread Visualization on Implementation of Stunting Prevention Program in Indonesia

Based on Figure 9, it is explained that the results of the Accelerated Reduction Efforts in Stunting Prevention Visualization Overlay are a recent, vibrant study with a total of 4322 links connecting various nodes. For further research development and specificity as additional references to assist in accelerating the reduction of stunting.

The implementation of stunting prevention programs in Indonesia involves various factors that need to be considered holistically to enhance intervention effectiveness (46). Based on the results of the Overlay Visualization analysis, data analysis from various districts is key to understanding the progress and distribution of programs, as well as identifying risk factors contributing to stunting prevalence. For example, using comprehensive databases, research can evaluate the relationship between sanitation, food security, and infant health conditions in different regions. This information is crucial for developing targeted intervention strategies and adapting policies relevant to local conditions.

Meta-analyses and scoping reviews can provide deep insights into the effectiveness of various stunting prevention programs in middle-income countries like Indonesia. This analysis not only evaluates the interventions undertaken but also identifies gaps in knowledge and policy that need to be addressed. By integrating data on risk factors such as associations between infant weight, mortality, and district policies, this research can provide a strong foundation for policymakers to design more effective and sustainable solutions to reduce stunting rates in Indonesia (47).

3. Density visualization

Density visualization in bibliometrics is a technique used to depict the distribution and concentration of bibliographic information in a compact graphical display (48). This technique allows researchers to visually understand how frequently specific keywords, research topics, or authors appear in related academic literature. In bibliometric analysis, density visualization is highly useful for identifying major trends, dominant research focuses, and information density across various fields or sub-fields of research.

Density visualization can also be employed to compare information density across different time periods or between countries with varying levels of development. By visualizing the evolution of topics and research trends over time, researchers can identify shifts in research approaches and focuses regarding stunting prevention. This is crucial for measuring knowledge advancement and identifying potential research directions for further exploration or development. Thus, density visualization in bibliometrics not only facilitates understanding of research structure and dynamics but also supports strategic planning to guide research activities and policy development in the field of stunting prevention.

Figure 10. Density Visualization in the Implementation of Stunting Prevention Program in Indonesia

Density visualization in bibliometric analysis is an important technique for identifying patterns and research trends in academic literature (49). In the context of analyzing 447 research articles related to the implementation of stunting prevention programs, several nodes or topics that are frequently studied include policy, access, birth, and household. These nodes indicate primary focuses in the related literature, with high item density reflecting extensive research efforts to explore these aspects.

The implementation of stunting prevention programs in Indonesia involves a deep understanding of various factors and variables influencing its success (20). From the findings of density visualization that identify frequently studied nodes such as policy, access, sanitation, and effectiveness, it can be observed that scholarly literature has extensively explored the relationships between these factors and stunting issues in various contexts.

Policy plays a crucial role in guiding and regulating the implementation of stunting prevention programs (50). Through density visualization, it is possible to analyze how various national and local policies influence community access to essential health, nutrition, and sanitation services needed to reduce stunting prevalence. Further research can identify effective policies in improving child health outcomes and the challenges that may arise in their implementation. Access to health and nutrition services is a critical factor in reducing stunting rates. Using data from density visualization, researchers can evaluate the extent to which adequate access to these essential services contributes to improving children's nutrition. This analysis is essential for developing more inclusive and evidence-based strategies to enhance healthcare accessibility in remote or high-risk areas in Indonesia. Sanitation plays a crucial role in child health and stunting prevention (51). By employing density visualization, researchers can map sanitation levels across various districts and understand how poor sanitation conditions contribute to high stunting rates. This can assist in designing more targeted interventions to improve household and community sanitation. Effectiveness of interventions is another key node frequently studied in the context of stunting prevention. From density visualization findings, researchers can evaluate various intervention strategies implemented in middle-income countries like Indonesia. This analysis helps identify the most successful approaches and factors that can enhance intervention effectiveness in the future, such as implementing more coordinated policies or participatory approaches with local communities.

Based on the research findings and discussion above, it can be assumed that further research is needed to conduct a similar study with specific modifications by adding mediation variables related to Community Engagement in interventions and policy implementation. Community engagement in interventions and policy implementation can significantly reduce the prevalence of stunting by facilitating better adoption of healthy nutrition and sanitation practices locally, strengthening program sustainability through active participation in planning and implementation, and building community capacity to promote sustainable behavioral changes at the individual and family levels. It is hoped that future research can develop a study on the Effectiveness of District-Level Interventions on Child Stunting by enhancing the mediation of Community Engagement in interventions and policy implementation.

4. CONCLUSION

Exploring the progress of research on the implementation of programs to reduce stunting in Indonesia using bibliometric analysis on ProQuest and VOSviewer, this study provides deep insights into recent trends and research focuses in this field. From the literature analysis, it is evident the significant contributions from researchers, institutions, and key concepts that are the main focal points. The findings of this research provide a solid foundation for assessing the effectiveness of efforts to reduce stunting, identifying collaboration opportunities, and formulating directions for future research. Visualization with VOSviewer also offers a graphical depiction that facilitates interpretation of results and provides a comprehensive overview of the research network related to efforts to decrease stunting prevalence.

In the implementation of stunting prevention programs in Indonesia, visual analysis of networks, distributions, and information density shows that active community engagement and policy effectiveness play crucial roles in reducing stunting rates. With active community participation in planning and program implementation, and the use of comprehensive data to identify local risks and needs, intervention strategies can be more accurately tailored. Factors such as adequate sanitation, access to adequate healthcare services, and efficient information management are key to enhancing program success. This approach aims not only to reduce stunting rates but also contributes to inclusive and sustainable health development for children in Indonesia.

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